

ODIN2025 - Oral and Dental Image aNalysis

challenges: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

ODIN2025 - Oral and Dental Image aNalysis challenges

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

ODIN2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are increasingly popular in modern dental practice, particularly for treatment planning or comprehensive prognosis evaluation [1*]. In dental applications, Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) and Intra-oral Scan (IOS) are 3D imaging techniques widely used for surgical planning and simulation [2*, 3*, 4*]. CBCT provides information on dental and maxillofacial structures, whereas IOS provides highly accurate surface information on tooth crowns and gingiva surfaces. In particular, segmentation of anatomical structures (e.g., teeth, pharynx, mandible) from CBCT and registration between CBCT and IOS is an essential prerequisite for surgical planning for dental implants or orthognathic surgery [1*, 5*]. Although the medical imaging community has proposed many solutions, these methods are trained and verified on a small, often private, amount of data, and their performances do not meet clinical requirements.

The main objective of our challenges is to push further the research on 3D dental image analysis, applying the rigorous approaches to performance evaluation needed in the medical field and calling for the latest results and techniques, which are often neglected by application-specific papers.

Our ODIN2025 initiative brings together two different challenge series, ToothFairy, and 3DTeethSeg, combining most of the image modalities involved in maxillofacial analysis, i.e., CBCTs and IOSs. Building on the success of our previous initiatives, with ODIN2025 we aim to further advance the understanding of cone beam computed tomography and intra-oral scans, addressing more complex data and structures and increasing the amount of training and testing sets. An ever-increasing effort in this edition is put into the clinical applicability of the participant solutions by considering not only performance but also typical constraints of daily clinical practice: time and resources.

Through this collaborative effort, we aim to pave the way for future multimodal image analysis that can more accurately and efficiently inform clinical decision-making, from diagnostics to treatment planning and post-surgical evaluations. The continued advancement in 3D dental imaging, along with improved segmentation, registration, and integration of CBCT and IOS data, holds the potential to revolutionize the way dental procedures are performed, ultimately benefiting both patients and practitioners alike.

[1*] Cui, Z., Fang, Y., Mei, L., Zhang, B., Yu, B., Liu, J., Jiang, C., Sun, Y., Ma, L., Huang, J., et al.: A fully automatic AI system for tooth and alveolar bone segmentation from cone-beam CT images. *Nature Communications* 13(1), 2096 (2022) 1

[2*] Flügge, T., Derksen, W., Te Poel, J., Hassan, B., Nelson, K., Wismeijer, D.: Registration of cone beam computed tomography data and intraoral surface scans—a prerequisite for guided implant surgery with cad/cam drilling guides. *Clinical Oral Implants Research* 28(9), 1113–1118 (2017) 1

[3*] Jamjoom, F.Z., Kim, D.G., McGlumphy, E.A., Lee, D.J., Yilmaz, B.: Positional accuracy of a prosthetic treatment plan incorporated into a cone beam computed tomography scan using surface scan registration. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry* 120(3), 367–374 (2018) 1

[4*] Kim, S., Choi, Y., Na, J., Song, I.S., Lee, Y.S., Hwang, B.Y., Lim, H.K., Baek, S.J.: Best of both modalities: Fusing CBCT and intraoral scan data into a single tooth image. In: *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. pp. 553–563. Springer (2024)

[5*] Rangel, F.A., Maal, T.J., de Koning, M.J., Bronkhorst, E.M., Berg'e, S.J., Kuijpers-Jagtman, A.M.: Integration of digital dental casts in cone beam computed tomography scans—a clinical validation study. *Clinical Oral Investigations* 22, 1215–1222 (2018).

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

CBCTs, 3D Intraoral Scan, Segmentation, Maxillofacial, 3D Volumes, Digital Orthodontics, 3D mesh, Dental Restoration, Interactive Segmentation, Latency Optimization

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

As the abstract mentions, the ODIN2025 challenge is a joint initiative that brings together ToothFairy and 3DTeethSeg challenges. With respect to ToothFairy and ToothFairy2 [1*], the related tasks introduce additional training data and a new private test set in order to include different acquisition machines and different patient populations. Additionally, the challenge introduces more hard-to-detect structures (thin and elongated shapes) to be segmented and favor fast and optimized algorithm proposals by introducing time as one of the main evaluation criteria: a good tradeoff between time and accuracy is mandatory to ensure the integration of automatic solutions in daily clinical practice. The number of labeled classes increased from 42 to 45.

A specific task for interactive segmentation is also designed with the goal of improving the accuracy in the segmentation of challenging structures like the Inferior Alveolar Canal (IAC). Indeed, while fully automated

segmentation models have shown promising results, their performance in the previous iterations of the ToothFairy challenges falls short of the accuracy required for clinical application. Leveraging user-provided clicks to refine segmentation outcomes will allow for improved performance and hold potential for further interactive human-in-the-loop annotation of this complex structure, enabling the creation of high-quality annotated datasets for future research.

With respect to 3DTeethSeg and 3DTeethLand challenges, which focused on teeth segmentation, labeling, and landmark detection tasks from intraoral 3D scans, the ODIN2025 edition introduces six distinct anatomical characteristics, including Natural Tooth, Implant Hole, Crown Preparation, and Abutment, and focus on their segmentation. The precise identification and analysis of these dental structures play a critical role in applications such as diagnosis, treatment planning, and the fabrication of dental prosthetics. Moreover, this edition will expand the Teeth3DS dataset [2*] to include more complex cases, particularly those involving damaged or missing teeth, making the dataset more representative of both orthodontics and restorative dentistry.

Overall, all the tasks aim to reduce potential ethnicity-related biases in anatomical variations in the evaluation by introducing previously unreleased data from different populations and different acquisition machines.

[1*] Bolelli, F., Lumetti, L., Vinayahalingam, S., Di Bartolomeo, M., Pellacani, A., Marchesini, K., ... & Grana, C. (2024). Segmenting the Inferior Alveolar Canal in CBCTs Volumes: the ToothFairy Challenge. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*.

[2*] Achraf Ben-Hamadou, Nour Neifar, Ahmed Rekik, Oussama Smaoui, Firas Bouzguenda, Sergi Pujades, Edmond Boyer, Edouard Ladoit "Teeth3DS+: An Extended Benchmark for Intraoral 3D Scans Analysis" arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.06094, 2022.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The tasks involved in the challenge are three in total:

1. 3DTeethSeg2: 3D Teeth Scan Segmentation and Labeling
2. ToothFairy3: Fast Multi-Structure Segmentation in CBCT Volumes
3. Interactive Segmentation of the Inferior Alveolar Canal in CBCT Volumes

Each of the tasks is detailed in the following sections. In summary, Task 1 and Task 2 relate to the segmentation of maxillofacial structures inside IOS and CBCT 3D volumes, respectively. Task 3 instead focuses on the interactive segmentation of hard-to-segment tubular structures, mainly focusing on the inferior alveolar canal in CBCT data.

Each task addresses specific real-world challenges faced by practitioners and researchers, paving the way for innovative applications in diagnostics, treatment planning, and post-operative evaluation. Below, we outline the primary application scenarios for each task:

- *Task 1, 2, 3 - Prosthetic Design and Fabrication*: Accurate segmentation of dental structures is essential for designing dental prostheses, such as crowns, bridges, and implants. By identifying specific features like implant holes or crown preparations, clinicians can ensure precise prosthetic fitting and alignment.
- *Task 1- Orthodontic Treatment Planning*: Detailed labeling and segmentation enable orthodontists to simulate tooth movements, assess occlusion, and design patient-specific appliances like aligners or braces in the context of

a complete digital workflow.

- *Task 1- Dental Arch Analysis*: Comprehensive analysis of the dental arch, including natural teeth and restorations, supports both diagnostic workflows and cosmetic dentistry.
- *Task 1, 2, 3 - Surgical Planning for Dental Implants*: Identification of anatomical structures such as teeth, mandible, and the inferior alveolar nerve allows surgeons to plan implant placement, avoiding critical structures and minimizing complications.
- *Task 2, 3 - Orthognathic Surgery Simulation*: Accurate segmentation of the maxilla, mandible, and adjacent structures supports surgical simulations and pre-operative evaluations, allowing to prepare optimal patient-specific surgical devices and ensuring more rapid and precise interventions.
- *Task 1, 2, 3 - Pathological Analysis*: Segmentation of dental and surrounding tissues aids in diagnosing conditions like cysts, tumors, or bone lesions, helping to understand their extension and providing a foundation for targeted treatments.
- *Task 2 - Mandibular Fracture Management*: Accurate delineation of the canal is vital for planning and executing surgical repairs of mandibular fractures, in a perspective of function-preservation.
- *Task 3 - Interactive Annotation for Dataset Creation*: User-assisted segmentation allows for the creation of high-quality annotated datasets, which can be used to train future AI models with improved accuracy for challenging structures.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

If accepted, this challenge will be part of the ODIN2025 workshop. Together with the STS challenge, we aim to create a strong consortium related to dental imaging research by covering most of the dental modalities involved in maxillofacial clinical practice: Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT), Intra Oral Scan (IOS), and X-rays.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

3 hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The challenge will require a three-hour slot but will hopefully be inserted into a full-day workshop event that will include an additional related challenge (STSR - Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration challenge), invited speakers, and discussions around dental imaging research.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We are expecting about 50 participating teams. The proposed challenge combines the ToothFairy challenge (third edition) and the 3DTeethSeg/Land (third edition).

ToothFairy received submissions (algorithms and associated description/paper) from ~20 different teams. During the onsite event, additional people (not belonging to any of the challenge participating teams) showed interest in

the event.

ToothFairy2 received almost 30 submissions from different teams.

3DTeethSeg and 3DTeethLand both received 14 final submissions

Potential participants are listed below (only those confirming their interest have been listed):

Yusheng Liu, Rui Xin, Tao Yang, Lisheng Wang, Yuxian Jiang [1*]

Haoshen Wang, Chenfan Xu, Zhiming Cui [2*]

Marek Wodzinski, Henning Müller, Yannick Kirchhoff, Maximilian R. Rokuss, Klaus Maier-Hein, Fabian Isensee [3*]

Jaehwan Han, Wan Kim, Tae-Hoon Yong, Byungsun Choi [4*]

Tomasz Szczepański, Michal K.Grzeszczyk, Przemyslaw Korzeniowski [5*]

Vicent Caselles Ballester [6*]

Konstantin Dmitriev [7*]

Shrajan Bhandary [8*]

Ajo Babu George [9*]

Zhaohong Pan [10*]

Affiliations:

[1*] Institute of Image Processing and Pattern Recognition, Department of Automation, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China

[2*] School of Biomedical Engineering, ShanghaiTech University, China

[3*] German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), Heidelberg, Division of Medical Image Computing, Germany

[4*] Osstem Implant Laboratory, Korea

[5*] Sano Centre for Computational Medicine, Poland

[6*] Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain

[7*] Overjet Inc, USA, New York

[8*] Cyber-Physical Systems, Technische Universität Wien, Vienna

[9*] Indian Institute of Technology, India, Kharagpur

[10*] Shenzhen Institute of Advanced Technology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, Shenzhen

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

All the members of the team submitting a solution to the final phases qualify as authors of the challenge submission. A paper summarizing the challenge results and including a description of each proposal will be published after the challenge: at most, two authors for each group may be eligible as authors of this paper. Our plan is to have a single joint publication summarizing and discussing all the tasks' results together.

All the participants are allowed to submit their own results in any venue (conferences, workshops, etc) with embargo restriction: 6 months after the MICCAI2025 event. An exception to the embargo will be given to papers submitted to the workshop associated with the challenge. This means that any of the challenge participants will be allowed to submit a paper describing the algorithmic solutions employed in the challenge to the ODIN2025 workshop. The embargo will still be valid for any other workshop/journal/conference venue.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We require standard technical equipment, including a projector, microphones, and a stable internet connection.

TASK 1: 3DTeethSeg2: 3D Teeth Scan Segmentation and Labeling Challenge

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Over the past four years, we have successfully launched the "3DTeethSeg" and "3DTeethLand" challenges, which focused on teeth segmentation, labeling, and landmark detection tasks from intraoral 3D scans. Building on the success of these initiatives, the latest challenge aims to further advance the understanding of intraoral scans by addressing more complex data and anatomical characteristics. This edition introduces six distinct anatomical characteristics, including Natural Tooth, Implant Hole, Crown Preparation, and Abutment, among others.

The precise identification and analysis of these dental structures play a critical role in applications such as diagnosis, treatment planning, and the fabrication of dental prosthetics. Automating these processes reduces the time and labor needed for manual annotation while improving accuracy and standardization in dental workflows. By addressing these challenges, this initiative aims to push the boundaries of AI in dentistry, tackling the complexity of intraoral data and driving innovation in automated dental analysis.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Digital Orthodontics, 3D Intraoral Scan, 3D Mesh, Dental Restoration

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizing team:

- Achraf Ben-Hamadou, Digital Research Center of Sfax, Tunisia
- Sergi Pujades, Inria, Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LJK, France
- Ahmed Rekik, Digital Research Center of Sfax, Tunisia
- Oussama Smaoui, Upperside Group, France
- Nour Neifar, Digital Research Center of Sfax, Tunisia
- Laura Montesdeoca Fenoy, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Natasha Hallberg, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Torkan Gholamalizadeh, 3Shape A/S, Denmark

Clinical Evaluators and Annotation Approvers:

- Margit Klinghammer, 3Shape A/S, Denmark

Data Contributor:

- 3Shape A/S, Denmark

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Achraf Ben-Hamadou, Digital Research Center of Sfax, Tunisia (achraf.benhamadou@gmail.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The challenge is associated with the MICCAI conference. The on-site event of the challenge will be a thematic event organized in conjunction with other challenges concerning similar topics (e.g., STSR - Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration challenge) in the framework of the oral and dental image analysis workshop (ODIN2025 workshop, proposal submitted to MICCAI2025).

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org or synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Webpage will be similar to the 3D Teeth Scan Segmentation and Labeling Challenge

(<https://crns-smartvision.github.io/teeth3ds/>). The website of the workshop hosting the challenges is available at www.odin-workshops.org/2025.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but no eligible for awards and will be listed in leaderboard with a clear identification marker

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Prospective sponsorship discussions are ongoing.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All team members qualify as authors of the challenge submission. A paper summarizing the challenge results and including a description of each proposal will be published after the challenge: at most two authors for each group may be eligible as authors of this paper. All the participants are allowed to submit their own results in any venue (conferences, workshops, etc.) with embargo restriction: 6 months after the MICCAI2025 event.

An exception to the embargo will be given to papers submitted to the workshop associated with the challenge. This means that any of the challenge participants will be allowed to submit a paper describing the algorithmic solutions employed in the challenge to the ODIN2025 workshop. The embargo will still be valid for any other workshop/journal/conference venue.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submission instructions will be on the webpage. We will let the participants submit their Docker submissions to the evaluation platform <https://grand-challenge.org> or <https://synapse.org/>.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Multiple submissions are allowed. However, only the last submission will be considered for the challenge results. Also, the number of Docker submissions will be limited to one per day.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration is open from 5th March, and will remain open until 31th August 2025, the deadline of the final docker submission.
 - 10th April 2025: Expected release of the training data.
 - 1st July 2025: Opening of the submission for the Preliminary Algorithm Submission Phase
 - 30th July 2025: Preliminary Algorithm Submission closes. Final Docker submission portal opens.
 - 31th August 2025. Final Docker submission deadline.
 - Announcement of results at Workshop/MICCAI 2025.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

All data are fully anonymized, and ethical approval is granted internally by the Legal Service of 3Shape (internal document BW-AA-190225). As the data collector and provider for the challenge, 3Shape also ensures compliance with GDPR.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code will be made public before the system is open for submission.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Not required; however, we encourage the participants to publish their code on GitHub or a similar platform.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

No conflicts of interest.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Assistance,CAD,Research,Education,Surgery,Training,Screening,Diagnosis,Prevention

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling

- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Localization, Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing dental restoration procedures.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Intraoral 3D scans for patient dentition requiring prosthetic treatment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Intraoral 3D scans.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional context information will be given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional context information will be given.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

For a given patient, the dataset may include a scan of the upper jaw, the lower jaw, or both.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The goal of the participating algorithms is to localize, segment and classify all objects (Gingiva, Natural Tooth, Implant Hole, Crown Preparation, Clasp Support Preparation, and Abutment) within a given intraoral 3D scan.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All data are acquired with state-of-the-art intraoral 3D scanners. All of the acquisitions are obtained from TRIOS IOS scanners from 3Shape. These scanners are representative and generate accurate 3D scans. No additional equipment other than the IOS scanner itself was used during the acquisitions.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

In general, no particular protocol is defined for the 3D intraoral scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

3D scans come from different clinics, mainly from Europe and Asia. All required clinical data are anonymized.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired by qualified professionals in dentistry, including orthodontists and dental surgeons.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

All data refers to an intraoral 3D scan of a dental arch from one patient. We made a data split by separating the patients to get:

- public training set (about 75%), this is the main data to be used for training and developing the participating algorithms.
- public testing set (10 additional cases only), these additional cases are used for a preliminary testing phase, focusing mainly on validating the functional aspect of the submitted algorithms.
- hidden testing set used for participant ranking (about 25%). This hidden dataset will be used for the final evaluation phase and serves as the final ranking of the competing algorithms.

Participant teams will have access only to public sets, i.e., training and testing.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

- Public training set: 3D scans acquired for 1.492 individual scans
- Public testing set: 3D scans acquired for 10 individual scans.
- Hidden testing set: 3D scans acquired for 498 individual scans.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Most state-of-the-art research works in this domain use a very limited number of scans, usually around 300 scans [1*], which means potentially under 200 patient use-cases. None of these are made publicly available. We believe that providing more representative use-cases considerably increases the number of publicly available data and can therefore trigger a boost in the research in this field. In the previous edition of the 3DTeethSeg challenge in 2022, we released 1,800 intraoral scans [2*], which represented the largest publicly available collection of intraoral scans at that time. This new edition of the challenge will expand the dataset with 2000 scans to include more representative cases and introduce additional label categories.

The new dataset is divided in a way to have enough data for training allowing enough variability between scans and subjects. We provide an additional set of 10 annotated scans to let the participants evaluate their algorithms in the preliminary test phase. This phase aims mainly to validate the functional aspect of the submitted solutions (output format, runtime, compatibility with the challenge platform etc.). Finally, the ranking score is computed based on the hidden testing set consisting of 498 scans. These will be accessible only to the organizers and the reviewers.

[1*] T. Kubík and M. Španěl, "Robust Teeth Detection in 3D Dental Scans by Automated Multi-view Landmarking," in Proceedings of the 15th International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies, 2022, pp. 24–34.

[2*] Achraf Ben-Hamadou, Nour Neifar, Ahmed Rekik, Oussama Smaoui, Firas Bouzguenda, Sergi Pujades,

Edmond Boyer, Edouard Ladrout "Teeth3DS+: An Extended Benchmark for Intraoral 3D Scans Analysis" arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.06094, 2022.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data comes from the data providers's Data Lake which contains data coming in from a lot of different dental clinics around the world. The data were collected from patients requiring dental restoration. Either after the restoration has been done, or after the teeth have been prepped but before placing the restoration.

There are over 15K teeth in the dataset, out of which 13641 (68.59%) are natural teeth. 2017 (10.14%) are crown preps. 1449 (7.29%) are bridge crowns. 854 (4.29%) are crowns. 518 (2.60%) are implant holes. 504 (2.53%) are inlay, onlay, or overlay. 386 (1.94%) are bridge pontic. And a few other minority classes.

The dataset contains 2000 dental arches, of which 1090 are upper jaws (54,5%) and 910 are lower jaws (45.5%).

In order to reduce biases to a minimum when evaluating algorithm performance, we put a lot of effort into the data collection. Specifically, the dataset has been acquired with patient demographics distributed all around the world, with the majority of scans coming from North America (~20%), Europe (~15%), and Asia (~45%).

Due to the data anonymization, we do not have access to all of the characteristics (e.g., sex and age), but we ensure that for the available characteristics (annotator, number of teeth in the scan, presence of different classes of objects in the scan) the train and test datasets have similar distributions.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

100% of the data proposed for this challenge edition is new and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotation process was carried out by professional annotators trained in the field of dentistry. A total of 5 annotators participated in the project. Each 3D scan was annotated by a single annotator; however, cross-validation was performed for identified corner cases and complex data. According to annotators, around 3-5% of cases required additional discussion. The complexity is mainly related to scan variations and different types of orthodontic constructions, which may need input from more experienced team members.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

All annotators must have read and understood the annotation protocol by 3Shape, which we cannot disclose as it is a commercial secret of the data provider. The Annotation Tool (internal 3Shape software) in version 1.1.0 or later must be used to conduct the annotation. The goal of this annotation is to identify different areas of a 3D

intraoral scan. Those can refer but are not limited to, hard and soft tissue, inorganic materials and dental restorative materials. If in doubt, the annotators can consult other colleagues or the supervisor of the annotation activity. There is also an internal loop for improving the data quality. Namely, if a problem has been discovered by testers of the products built using the annotations, the annotated cases that potentially have this problem are being reannotated, the annotators informed, and the annotation guidelines might be updated. This process guarantees the high quality of the annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

An annotator should be educated as a certified dental technician or dentist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotation protocol adopted involves a single annotator for each case, meaning that no aggregation is required. However, cross-validation was performed for the identification of corner cases and complex data.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No preprocessing steps are required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Each 3D scan is attributed to only one annotator. Meaning there was no additional validation or inter-annotator comparison. This could be reflected in the preciseness of the annotations. Resulting in local errors, especially around the interproximal area, and increasingly so if deposits are present in the scan. We plan to involve different annotators to independently reannotate a portion of each test set ($\geq 20\%$) involved in the challenge. The re-annotation will be performed following the same protocols described in this document and will be used to compare the accuracy of the challenge submissions with the annotators' inter-agreement in the paper describing the challenge results. We do not plan to use such re-annotations for evaluating challenge submissions.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- Object Localization Precision (OLP): Measures the mean normalized Euclidean distance between ground truth (GT) object centroids and their closest detected centroids. A nominal penalty is applied for missing detections.

- Object Numbering Accuracy (ONA): The accuracy of correctly predicting object numbers, expressed as the percentage of correctly numbered cases relative to all ground truth objects in the test set. The attribution strategy is based on the distance between GT and the closest detected object centroid.

-Object Classification Accuracy (OCA): The accuracy of correctly classifying objects, calculated as the percentage of correctly classified cases relative to all ground truth objects in the test set. The attribution strategy is identical to that used for calculating ONA.

Pointcloud segmentation metrics:

- The average Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) over all object instances.

- Mean Surface Average Distance (MASD): defined as the mean of the average over all shortest distances from all sampled points on one boundary to any other point on another boundary.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

These metrics were validated in the 3DTeethSeg'22 challenge [1*], where they demonstrated their robustness in benchmarking segmentation and labeling algorithms for dental applications [2*].

Object Localization Precision(OLP) and Object Numbering Accuracy (ONA) together capture the algorithm's ability to accurately identify and localize dental structures, ensuring precise detection and numbering of objects. Object Classification Accuracy (OCA) further evaluates the classification accuracy, which is essential for distinguishing between various dental components like natural teeth and implants.

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) as an overlap-based segmentation metric provides a detailed evaluation of 3D point labeling, directly reflecting the quality of teeth segmentation, which is critical for accurate treatment planning and device fabrication.

Finally, to enforce DSC we introduce Mean Average Surface Distance (MASD) as a boundary-based penalization metric with a contour focus, ensuring precise delineation of object edges, a key factor for prosthodontic applications.

The addition of the MASD is important as discussion with practitioners highlighted the importance of the definition of sharp boundaries.

The choice of the DSC and MASD metrics was performed with the help of the Metrics Reloaded webpage. [3*] (<https://metrics-reloaded.dkfz.de/metric?id=masd>)

[1*] Ben-Hamadou, Achraf, et al. "3DTeethSeg'22: 3D Teeth Scan Segmentation and Labeling Challenge." arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.18277 (2023).

[2*] Rekik, Ahmed, et al. "TSegLab: Multi-stage 3D dental scan segmentation and labeling." *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 185 (2025): 109535.

[3*] Reinke, Annika, et al. "Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation." *Nature Methods* 21.2 (2024): 182-194.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will adopt a point-based ranking method coupled with the bootstrapping technique to enhance the ranking robustness.

The procedure involves:

1. Computation of metrics;
2. For each metric, teams are pairwise compared using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. The team deemed “statistically better” ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$) in each comparison receives one point. This process yields a “total point count” for each team, reflecting the number of times it outperformed its counterparts.
3. Bootstrapping: Apply bootstrapping as 10% of the data is resampled and step 2 is repeated for the remaining data. This generates a 'total point count' per team for each dropped data.
4. Aggregation of 'total point counts' to determine the final ranking.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing data in the algorithm output (e.g., wrong segmentations for certain cases or failure to localize objects...) is permitted but implicitly affects the DSC and ONA/OCA scores, with OLP being managed as outlined in “Metric Definition”.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

This ranking method was used in several challenges, such as 3DTeethLand, BraTS [*1], Medical Segmentation Decathlon [*2], VerSe'20 [*3] and Dentex [*4]. Participants have provided positive feedback, primarily for the stability of this method in outlying performances.

[1*] B. H. Menze et al., “The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS),” *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1993–2024, 2015.

[2*] M. Antonelli et al., “The Medical Segmentation Decathlon,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 4128, 2022.

[3*] A. Sekuboyina et al., “VerSe: A Vertebrae labelling and segmentation benchmark for multi-detector CT images,” *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 73, p. 102166, 2021.

[4*] I. E. Hamamci et al., “DENTEX: An Abnormal Tooth Detection with Dental Enumeration and Diagnosis Benchmark for Panoramic X-rays.” *arXiv*, 2023.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The proposed statistical analysis to rank participants is based on Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap method. Missing data is handled as described in 27.b/26.a.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This statistical method was used in several challenges, such as 3DTeethLand, BraTS [*1], Medical Segmentation Decathlon [*2], VerSe'20 [*3] and Dentex [*4]. Participants have provided positive feedback, primarily for the stability of this method in outlying performances.

[1*] B. H. Menze et al., "The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS)," *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1993–2024, 2015.

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[3*] A. Sekuboyina et al., "VerSe: A Vertebrae labelling and segmentation benchmark for multi-detector CT images," *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 73, p. 102166, 2021.

[4*] I. E. Hamamci et al., "DENTEX: An Abnormal Tooth Detection with Dental Enumeration and Diagnosis Benchmark for Panoramic X-rays." *arXiv*, 2023.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

There is no further analysis applicable that is not discussed above.

TASK 2: ToothFairy3: Fast Multi-class Segmentation in CBCT Volumes

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The use of Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) is increasing in dentistry and in the whole field of head, neck, and maxillofacial surgery. The main advantages of CBCTs are related to the short acquisition time and the low radiation dose while maintaining an excellent visualization of anatomical structures, especially of hard tissues. In this regard, with ToothFairy - MICCAI2023, we initially tackled the segmentation of the Inferior Alveolar Canal (IAC), a noble structure that lies within the mandible, whose identification and preservation represent a primary objective of many surgical interventions. In the following edition, ToothFairy2 - MICCAI2024, we increased the number of anatomical structures to be considered in the segmentation, thus including the mandible, the teeth, the maxillary bone, and the pharynx (42 classes in total). Their framing is cross-disciplinary, as they are involved in all the head and neck surgical specialties, as well as in clinical and anesthesiological daily practice. In this regard, deep learning models can support medical personnel in surgical planning procedures by providing an automatic voxel-level segmentation.

With ToothFairy3 - MICCAI2025, we aim to push the development of deep learning frameworks to segment anatomical structures in CBCTs by incrementally extending the amount of publicly available 3D-annotated CBCT scans and providing additional segmentation classes for existing and specifically introduced data. New classes will include pulp chamber and root canals, incisive nerves, and the lingual foramen (45 classes in total). All of these structures, missing in the previous editions of the challenge, are essential for effective orthodontic interventions.

Given the high performance of ToothFairy2 submissions in most of the classes involved, this year, our goal is twofold: introducing more challenging structures (thin and elongated) to be segmented and favor fast and optimized algorithm proposals by introducing time as one of the main evaluation criteria and not using it only as tie-breaker. A good tradeoff between time and accuracy is mandatory to ensure the integration of automatic solutions in daily clinical practice.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

CBCTs, Segmentation, 3D Volumes, Maxillofacial, Latency Optimization

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

- Federico Bolelli, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

- Luca Lumetti, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

- Shankeeth Vinayahalingam, Radboud University, Netherlands
- Niels van Nistelrooij, Radboud University, Netherlands
- Mattia Di Bartolomeo, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
- Kevin Marchesini, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Vittorio Pipoli, University of Pisa, Italy
- Paolo Minafra, Affidea, Italy
- Torkan Gholamalizadeh, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Laura Montesdeoca Fenoy, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Natasha Hallberg, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Alexandre Anesi, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Costantino Grana, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Federico Bolelli, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy (federico.bolelli@unimore.it)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The challenge is associated with the MICCAI conference. The on-site event of the challenge will be a thematic event organized in conjunction with other challenges concerning similar topics (e.g., STSR - Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration challenge) in the framework of the oral and dental image analysis workshop (ODIN2025 workshop, proposal submitted to MICCAI2025).

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

The platform used to run the platform challenge will be grand-challenge.org. Previous challenge editions are available at <https://toothfairy.grand-challenge.org/> and <https://toothfairy2.grand-challenge.org/>.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

A specific website will be implemented and available at <https://toothfairy3.grand-challenge.org/>. The website of the workshop hosting the challenges is available at www.odin-workshops.org/2025

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but no eligible for awards and will be listed in leaderboard with a clear identification marker

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge will award the first three classified institutions/research groups. For each institution/research group, only the last submission will be considered for the final ranking. The amount of the prizes will be in line with that of the previous editions and will be around 3.000 € in total. See Through S.r.l.

(<https://www.seethrough.one/>) will sponsor the challenge.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be announced publicly, and they must share their code in a public repository (e.g., GitHub). If the submission authors do not publicly share the code with the appropriate README for replicating the experiments, the prize(s) will shift to the next classified institution(s).

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All team members qualify as authors of the challenge submission. A paper summarizing the challenge results and including a description of each proposal will be published after the challenge: at most two authors for each group may be eligible as authors of this paper. All the participants are allowed to submit their own results in any venue (conferences, workshops, etc.) with embargo restriction: 6 months after the MICCAI2025 event.

An exception to the embargo will be given to papers submitted to the workshop associated with the challenge. This means that any of the challenge participants will be allowed to submit a paper describing the algorithmic solutions employed in the challenge to the ODIN2025 workshop. The embargo will still be valid for any other workshop/journal/conference venue.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Since the test dataset cannot be released, all the participants would submit a Docker container or a GitHub repository, following the template that we will provide at <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy> in case of challenge acceptance. The submission instructions will be detailed at <https://toothfairy3.grand-challenge.org/how-to-submit/>.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To verify compliance with submission policies, participating teams can have multiple submissions during the debugging phase. The number of submissions per day per team is limited to 1. This phase will leverage a few volumes extracted from the training set and is intended for debugging purposes only.

To verify the quality of their methods and confirm compliance with submission policies, participating teams will have three submissions during the preliminary evaluation phase. Each submission will be evaluated on three volumes extracted from the entire test set, and the results will be displayed on a live leaderboard.

During the final evaluation phase, only one submission per team is allowed. The leaderboard associated with this phase will be used for the final ranking.

Participants are not allowed to submit multiple solutions under a different team name or using different accounts. If identified, all of the submissions violating the abovementioned rules will be removed from the final ranking, and associated participants will be disqualified.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

The challenge schedule is defined as follows:

- Release of training cases: 10th April 2025;
- Release of test cases: test cases will not be publicly released;
- Submission date(s):
- from 1st July 2025 to 31st July 2025 included (debugging phase);

- from 1st August 2025 to 15th August 2025 (preliminary test phase);
- from 8th August 2025 to 15th August 2025 (final test phase);
- Release date of the results: 15th September 2025;
- Associated workshop days: 23-27 September 2025.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Data composing the training set have already received the approval of the ethical committee and they can be shared for research purposes only. More specifically, the ethical approval was obtained from Comitato Etico dell'Area Vasta Emilia Nord (Approval Number 1374/2020/OSS/ESTMO SIRER ID 1275 - NAI-CBCT-D).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code used to evaluate the submissions, as well as the whole source code of the website will be publicly available on GitHub. The link pointing to the aforementioned repository will be placed on the challenge website: <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy>.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

As previously mentioned, the top three performing methods must share their code on a public repository (e.g., GitHub). To be considered for the post-challenge publication, teams must make their algorithm publicly available (e.g., on a GitHub repository) as well as the network's parameters. An appropriate license must be selected. Regardless, all the participants are warmly invited to do so, thus guaranteeing reproducible research and results.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Members of the companies that will be sponsors of the challenge can participate with submission, but will not be eligible for prizes. As mentioned, the test set will not be publicly released.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis,Treatment planning,Research,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation

- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Final biomedical applications will acquire data using standard CBCT scanning protocol.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The target cohort includes patients older than 16 years who performed a CBCT for monitoring or surgery planning. Only CBCTs that were unreadable or where there was a massive alteration of the normal anatomy (mainly due to previous surgical resective procedures) have been excluded, thus allowing a wide variability close to a real clinical setting. The target cohort and the challenge cohort (should) match since the challenge dataset has been acquired in a real-case scenario

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CBCTs

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Along with the images, a ground-truth segmentation is provided in the form of an image, i.e., a 3D volume having the same spatial size of the image data with zero values corresponding to the background and a unique integer identifier for each different anatomical structure.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No patient clinical data is provided.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The lower and upper jaws of the patients were acquired by means of cone beam computed tomography.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm must target the different anatomical structures in the jaws by providing a volume where each voxel is identified with an integer value corresponding to the detected anatomical structure.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Runtime, Precision, Reliability, Sensitivity, Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All the data of the training set has been obtained using a NewTom/NTVGiMK4, 3 mA, 110 kV, 0.3 mm cubic voxels. The scans of the private test set have been obtained from two different sources. Data coming from Radboud Medical Center are obtained using a standard CBCT scanning protocol (i-CAT, 3D Imaging System, Imaging Sciences International Inc, Hatfield, PA, USA) in "Extended Field" modus (FOV: 16 cm diameter/22 cm height; scan time: 2 x 20s; voxel size: 0.4 mm). Scans provided by 3Shape A/S have been obtained using PaX-Flex3D and Implagraphy devices produced by VATECH Co., Ltd. with FOV: 12 cm diameter/8.4 cm height, current and voltage of 4 mA, 89 kV, and isotropic voxel spacing of 0.3 mm).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Pixel spacing and intra-slice distance is always 0.3 millimeters. Data volumes have already been converted to the Hounsfield Unit (HU), and their values range between -1000 and 5264. Volume shapes range from (170, 272, 345) to (266, 512, 512) for the Z, Y and X axes, respectively.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The 3D CBCT volumes composing training dataset have been acquired by the Affidea center located in Modena, Italy. Affidea is a leading pan-European healthcare group specialized in the provision of advanced diagnostics, specialist outpatient services, laboratory analyses, physiotherapy and rehabilitation, cancer diagnosis and treatment. It has 312 centers in 15 different countries, with about 11,000 professionals. The test set is from

3Shape A/S and the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at Radboud University Medical Center.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Medical experts with many (>5) years of experience performed both data acquisition and annotation tasks.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Both training and test cases are CBCT volumes of the jaws. Although every test case entails a thorough scan of the entire targeted anatomical structures, the training set exhibits variations in the field of view. Specifically, within a subset of the training cases, there may be instances where a portion of the upper jaw as well as the upper teeth are partially absent. Regardless, each case is associated with a 3D annotation where each anatomical structure is identified with a unique integer value.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training dataset is composed of more than 500 volumes, and the test set is composed of 50 volumes. All the training volumes will be provided with a complete annotation. While we provide an "official" split setting for the public data, each challenge participant is free to decide how to split training data to create an internal validation set.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset is divided to have enough data (more than 500 patient use-cases) for training, allowing enough variability between scans and subjects. The test set comprises a number of cases that are obtained from two different sources, i.e., Radboud University Medical Center and 3Shape A/S, which ensures a robust evaluation of algorithm performance under different perspectives. Having more (and more) data as a training set is always helpful but expensive and time-consuming (extremely so). The current amount of training data selected for the challenge represents the most significant training set available in literature at the moment of writing this proposal.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

As mentioned, the test set will not be released for ethical concerns. We chose to use a set of data coming from different institutions to keep the training set as big as possible. Every patient was anonymized, and we only kept a

few personal details —namely gender, age, and year of the scan. When selecting the test cases, we ensured that the clinical distributions (i.e., age, sex, etc.) and the annotators were aligned with those of the training set. Additionally, when splitting the data, acquisition machines and patient demographics were strictly separated to prevent overlap between the training and test sets, ensuring a clear separation and promoting model generalization while discouraging the exploitation of acquisition or demographic biases.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

100% (50 cases) of the test set is unpublished and never used in previous challenges.

~10% (50 cases) of the training data is previously unseen.

Annotations for three new classes are provided for 100% of the training and test data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All the annotations have been obtained by means of a specifically developed software that allows experts to annotate each image data. Annotators are doctors with more than 5 years of experience. The total number of annotators involved is 7.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotators are medical experts, and the annotation tool has been developed following their instructions/requirements, maximizing annotation accuracy. The medical team involved in the development of the tool also directly participates in the annotation process, ensuring that the criteria used are consistent and agreed upon by all institutions involved. Although formal annotation guidelines were not strictly necessary, each annotation is validated by at least one additional expert to reduce inconsistencies and ensure fairness in evaluation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Every case has been annotated by medical experts with more than five years of experience in the maxillofacial field.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available in our scenario, meaning that each CBCT volume is annotated by a single expert only, but each produced annotation has been validated or corrected by at least another annotator to reduce possible mistakes.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All the volumes have been rescaled to have the same voxel size (0.3mm isotropic) and rescaled to HU (Hounsfield Unit).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Volumes have been manually annotated by medical experts, but no multiple annotations are available for the same CBCT. We plan to involve different annotators to independently reannotate a portion of each test set ($\geq 20\%$) involved in the challenge. The re-annotation will be performed following the same protocols described in this document and will be used to compare the accuracy of the challenge submissions with the annotators' inter-agreement in the paper describing the challenge results. We do not plan to use such re-annotations for evaluating challenge submissions.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

No other relevant source of error has been identified.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The metric used to rank the submitted proposals is the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), the 95th percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95), and the inference execution time (Time). Furthermore, the maximum memory usage will be used. Please refer to the ranking method(s) section for more details.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Together with IoU (Intersection over Union), DSC represents the current practice for the evaluation of segmentation algorithms. Since their meaning is practically the same, there is no reason to preserve both metrics. The average Hausdorff Distance is a widely used performance measure employed in medical image segmentation as it provides a distance between two point sets, which is extremely relevant in clinical applications.

Metrics Reloaded (<https://metrics-reloaded.dkfz.de/>) recommendations have been employed to select the most appropriate metrics. Among the suggested metrics there were the Dice score and the Normalized Surface Distance (NSD). Compared to the Hausdorff Distance (HD), the NSD is less sensitive to the outliers. We opted for the HD95 as, for example, measuring the distance between the inferior alveolar nerve and the teeth roots requires an error upper bound instead of the average error. This allows practitioners to carefully plan surgical operations for teeth removal while preventing any risk of damaging the nerve.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking schema involves the following steps:

1. For each class and for each volume, calculate the Dice score (DSC) and the HD95. Measure also the inference time (Time) and the maximum used memory (Mem);
2. Average the DSC and the HD95 for each class across all volumes and compute the average Time across all volumes.
3. Rank all the DSC, HD95, Time, and maximum used memory independently;
4. Average the rankings obtained at point 3 for each DSC, HD95, and Time to produce the final rank. Average Time is weighted as much as the number of classes included in the dataset to balance its importance with respect to the other metrics;
5. If two or more final ranks obtained at point 4 are equal, Mem will be used to break ties;
6. If two or more ranks are still equal, it is a tie: the prize will be evenly split.

Point 3 will generate 92 rankings (45 classes * 2 metrics + Time ranking + Mem ranking). Point 4 will compute the average of 90 rankings (45 classes * 2 metrics) weighted as 1 and the single Time ranking weighted as 45. Mem ranking will be used only as a tiebreaker (point 6).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm does not produce any result for a specific CBCT volume, we will consider the predicted segmentation as a volume of 0s, meaning that the Dice score for that image will be equal to 0 for each class, and the HD95 will be equal to the diagonal of the volume. Furthermore, the inference time will be set at 10 minutes for this case.

The evaluation code will be publicly available to be reviewed by participants at <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy/blob/main/ToothFairy3/Multi-Instance-Segmentation/evaluation/evaluation.py>

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

There is no interdependence between patients/cases. Each CBCT (both in train and test) belongs to a different patient and has been annotated by only one expert. The selected metrics will provide homogeneous numbers on different patients that can be later averaged to provide the final rank on a specific class/metric. Different metrics (i.e., DSC and Hausdorff distance) calculated separately on each class are later aggregated to produce the final ranking.

To ensure robustness in the final ranking, the recommendations provided by Maier et al. [1*] have been followed. In general, there are two contrasting approaches to aggregate metrics across the test cases. The first approach, known as metric-based aggregation, involves initially aggregating metric values across all test cases (e.g., using mean or median), and then ranking the algorithms on the aggregated value. The second approach is case-based aggregation, which starts by calculating a rank for each test case, and then the final rank is determined by aggregating the ranks of the test cases. According to the paper by Maier et al. [1*], the single-metric rankings

(specifically for DSC and HD95 in our case) demonstrate higher statistical robustness when employing metric-based aggregation and using the mean instead of the median for aggregation.

[1*] Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A., Onogur, S., Stankovic, M., Scholz, P., Arbel, T., Bogunovic, H., Bradley, A.P., Carass, A., et al., 2018. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. *Nature Communications* 9, 5217

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will perform bootstrapping to assess ranking uncertainty.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The final top-ranked participant will represent the optimal balance of model effectiveness and model latency. Although the top-ranked method may not be the most effective in terms of DSC and HD95, it will be the easiest method to integrate into daily clinical practice, as it predicts effective results close to the state of the art while providing these results at a reasonable latency. Furthermore, the actual metric values are converted to per-metric rankings to increase the variability across methods, and the final post-challenge ranking of the submissions will be determined using bootstrapping to limit the selection bias for the volumes in the test set.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the challenge summary paper we plan to discuss and evaluate ranking variability, inter-algorithm variability, and the combination of submitted algorithms via ensembling.

TASK 3: Interactive Segmentation of the Inferior Alveolar Canal in CBCT Volumes

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The Inferior Alveolar Canal (IAC) is a critical anatomical structure located within the mandible and is essential for many dental and surgical interventions. Accurate segmentation of the IAC in Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) scans remains challenging due to its fine-grained nature and variability across patients. While fully automated segmentation models have shown promising results, their performance in the previous iterations of the ToothFairy challenges falls short of the accuracy required for clinical application.

To address this gap, we propose focusing on interactive segmentation of the IAC, leveraging user-provided clicks to refine segmentation outcomes. Click-based interactive models provide a powerful mechanism for clinical experts to directly convey their knowledge to segmentation models, enabling precise control over what is segmented with minimal user input, such as a few well-placed clicks, thereby enhancing both accuracy and clinical feasibility. These models not only improve IAC segmentation for potential clinical use but also enable further interactive human-in-the-loop annotation of this complex structure, enabling the creation of high-quality annotated datasets for future research.

We introduce an interactive segmentation task to foster innovation in this domain, inviting participants to develop and submit click-based interactive models tailored for IAC segmentation in CBCT scans. This task also provides an opportunity for participants to leverage and build upon emerging prompt-based foundation models, further advancing the state-of-the-art in interactive medical image segmentation. By focusing on the interactive domain, we aim to bridge the gap between automated solutions and clinical requirements, ultimately supporting more precise surgical planning and improving patient outcomes.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

CBCTs, Interactive Segmentation, 3D Volumes, Inferior Alveolar Canals, Clicks

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

- Zdravko Marinov, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
- Federico Bolelli, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Luca Lumetti, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Shankeeth Vinayahalingam, Radboud University, Netherlands

- Niels van Nistelrooij, Radboud University, Netherlands
- Mattia Di Bartolomeo, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
- Kevin Marchesini, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Paolo Minafra, Affidea, Italy
- Torkan Gholamalizadeh, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Laura Montesdeoca Fenoy, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Natasha Hallberg, 3Shape A/S, Denmark
- Alexandre Anesi, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- Rainer Stiefelhagen, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
- Costantino Grana, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Federico Bolelli, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy (federico.bolelli@unimore.it)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The challenge is associated with the MICCAI conference. The on-site event of the challenge will be a thematic event organized in conjunction with other challenges concerning similar topics (e.g., STSR - Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration challenge) in the framework of the oral and dental image analysis workshop (ODIN2025 workshop, proposal submitted to MICCAI2025).

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

The platform used to run the platform challenge will be grand-challenge.org. Previous challenge editions are available at <https://toothfairy.grand-challenge.org/> and <https://toothfairy2.grand-challenge.org/>.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

A specific website will be implemented and available at <https://toothfairy3.grand-challenge.org/>. The website of the workshop hosting the challenges is available at www.odin-workshops.org/2025.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic, Semi automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but no eligible for awards and will be listed in leaderboard with a clear identification marker

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge will award the first three classified institutions/research groups. For each institution/research group, only the last submission will be considered for the final ranking. The amount of the prizes will be in line with that of the previous editions and will be around 3.000 € in total. See Through S.r.l. (<https://www.seethrough.one/>) will sponsor the challenge.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be announced publicly, and they must share their code in a public repository (e.g., GitHub). If the submission authors do not publicly share the code with the appropriate README for replicating the experiments, the prize(s) will shift to the next classified institution(s).

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All team members qualify as authors of the challenge submission. A paper summarizing the challenge results and including a description of each proposal will be published after the challenge: at most two authors for each group may be eligible as authors of this paper. All the participants are allowed to submit their own results in any venue (conferences, workshops, etc.) with embargo restriction: 6 months after the MICCAI2025 event.

An exception to the embargo will be given to papers submitted to the workshop associated with the challenge. This means that any of the challenge participants will be allowed to submit a paper describing the algorithmic solutions employed in the challenge to the ODIN2025 workshop. The embargo will still be valid for any other workshop/journal/conference venue.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Since the test dataset cannot be released, all the participants would submit a Docker container or a GitHub repository, following the template that we will provide at <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy> in case of challenge acceptance. The submission instructions will be detailed at <https://toothfairy3.grand-challenge.org/how-to-submit/>.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To verify compliance with submission policies, participating teams can have multiple submissions during the debugging phase. The number of submissions per day per team is limited to 1. This phase will leverage a few volumes extracted from the training set and is intended for debugging purposes only.

To verify the quality of their methods and confirm compliance with submission policies, participating teams will have three submissions during the preliminary evaluation phase. Each submission will be evaluated on three volumes extracted from the entire test set, and the results will be displayed on a live leaderboard.

During the final evaluation phase, only one submission per team is allowed. The leaderboard associated with this phase will be used for the final ranking.

Participants are not allowed to submit multiple solutions under a different team name or using different accounts. If identified, all of the submissions violating the abovementioned rules will be removed from the final ranking, and associated participants will be disqualified.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

The challenge schedule is defined as follows:

- Release of training cases: 10th April 2025;
- Release of test cases: test cases will not be publicly released;
- Submission date(s):
- from 1st July 2025 to 31st July 2025 included (debugging phase);
- from 1st August 2025 to 15th August 2025 (preliminary test phase);

- from 8th August 2025 to 15th August 2025 (final test phase);
- Release date of the results: 15th September 2025;
- Associated workshop days: 23-27 September 2025.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Data composing the training set have already received the approval of the ethical committee and they can be shared for research purposes only. More specifically, the ethical approval was obtained from Comitato Etico dell'Area Vasta Emilia Nord (Approval Number 1374/2020/OSS/ESTMO SIRER ID 1275 - NAI-CBCT-D).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code used to evaluate the submissions, as well as the whole source code of the website will be publicly available on GitHub. The link pointing to the aforementioned repository will be placed on the challenge website: <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy>.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

As previously mentioned, the top three performing methods must share their code on a public repository (e.g., GitHub). To be considered for the post-challenge publication, teams must make their algorithm publicly available (e.g., on a GitHub repository) as well as the network's parameters. An appropriate license must be selected. Regardless, all the participants are warmly invited to do so, thus guaranteeing reproducible research and results.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Members of the companies that will be sponsors of the challenge can participate with submission, but will not be eligible for prizes. As mentioned, the test set will not be publicly released.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis,Treatment planning,Research,Training,Semi-automatic annotation

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation

- Tracking

Segmentation, Interactive Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Final biomedical applications will acquire data using standard CBCT scanning protocol.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The target cohort includes patients older than 16 years who performed a CBCT for monitoring or surgery planning. Only CBCTs that were unreadable or where there was a massive alteration of the normal anatomy (mainly due to previous surgical resective procedures) have been excluded, thus allowing a wide variability close to a real clinical setting. The target cohort and the challenge cohort (should) match since the challenge dataset has been acquired in a real-case scenario

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CBCTs

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Along with the images, a ground-truth segmentation is provided in the form of an image, i.e., a 3D volume having the same spatial size of the image data with 0 values corresponding to the background and 1 and 2 values corresponding to the left and right Inferior Alveolar Canals (IACs), respectively. Additionally, each image will include supplementary data in the form of a set of a fixed number of 3D click coordinates of voxels belonging to each IAC (5 clicks per IAC branch, 10 clicks in total). To ensure fairness and consistency in evaluating interactive methods, all participants will receive an identical set of pre-generated clicks for all training and test cases.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No patient clinical data is provided.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The lower and upper jaws of the patients were acquired by means of cone beam computed tomography.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm must target the inferior alveolar canals (IACs) present in the lower jaw, by providing a volume where each voxel is identified with an integer value corresponding to the detected class (background: 0, left IAC: 1, right IAC: 2).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Reliability, Sensitivity, Specificity, Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All the data of the training set has been obtained using a NewTom/NTVGiMK4, 3 mA, 110 kV, 0.3 mm cubic voxels. The scans of the private test set have been obtained from two different sources. Data coming from Radboud Medical Center are obtained using a standard CBCT scanning protocol (i-CAT, 3D Imaging System, Imaging Sciences International Inc, Hatfield, PA, USA) in "Extended Field" modus (FOV: 16 cm diameter/22 cm height; scan time: 2 x 20s; voxel size: 0.4 mm). Scans provided by 3Shape A/S have been obtained using PaX-Flex3D and Implagraphy devices produced by VATECH Co., Ltd. with FOV: 12 cm diameter/8.4 cm height, current and voltage of 4 mA, 89 kV, and isotropic voxel spacing of 0.3 mm).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Pixel spacing and intra-slice distance is always 0.3 millimeters. Data volumes have already been converted to the Hounsfield Unit (HU), and their values range between -1000 and 5264. Volume shapes range from (170, 272, 345) to (266, 512, 512) for the Z, Y and X axes, respectively.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The 3D CBCT volumes composing the training dataset have been acquired by the Affidea center located in Modena, Italy. Affidea is a leading pan-European healthcare group specialized in the provision of advanced

diagnostics, specialist outpatient services, laboratory analyses, physiotherapy and rehabilitation, cancer diagnosis and treatment. It is active in 312 different centers in 15 different countries, with about 11,000 professionals. The test set is from the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery in Radboud University Medical Center and 3Shape A/S.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Medical experts with many (>5) years of experience performed both data acquisition and annotation tasks.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Both training and test cases are CBCT volumes of the jaws. Although every test case entails a thorough scan of the entire maxillofacial field of view comprising all the targeted anatomical structures, the training set exhibits variations in the field of view. Specifically, within a subset of the training cases, there may be instances where a portion of the upper jaw as well as the upper teeth, are partially absent. Each case is associated with a 3D annotation where each IAC is identified with two unique integer values, one corresponding to the left canal and one to right one. Each case is also supplemented with a set of five pre-simulated user clicks for each IAC present in the CBCT scan.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training dataset is composed of more than 500 volumes and 50 volumes are used as a test set. All the training volumes will be provided with a complete 3D annotation and five pre-simulated user clicks per IAC. While we provide an "official" split setting for the public data, each challenge participant is free to decide how to split training data to create an internal validation set.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset is divided to have enough data (more than 500 patient use-cases) for training, allowing enough variability between scans and subjects. The test set comprises a number of cases that are obtained from two different sources, i.e., Radboud University Medical Center and 3Shape A/S, which ensures a robust evaluation of algorithm performance under different perspectives. Having more (and more) data as a training set is always helpful but expensive and time-consuming (extremely so). The current amount of training data selected for the challenge represents the most significant training set available in literature at the moment of writing this proposal.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

As mentioned, the test set will not be released for ethical concerns. We chose to use a set of data coming from different institutions to keep the training set as big as possible. Every patient was anonymized, and we only kept a few personal details —namely gender, age, and year of the scan. When selecting the test cases, we ensured that the clinical distributions (i.e., age, sex, etc.) and the annotators were aligned with those of the training set. Additionally, when splitting the data, acquisition machines and patient demographics were strictly separated to prevent overlap between the training and test sets, ensuring a clear separation and promoting model generalization while discouraging the exploitation of acquisition or demographic biases.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

100% (50 cases) of the test set is unpublished and never used in previous challenges.

~10% (50 cases) of the training data is previously unseen.

Annotations for three new classes are provided for 100% of the training and test data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All the annotations have been obtained by means of a specifically developed software that allows experts to annotate each image data. Annotators are doctors with more than 5 years of experience. The total number of annotators involved is 7.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotators are medical experts, and the annotation tool has been developed following their instructions/requirements, maximizing annotation accuracy. The medical team involved in the development of the tool also directly participates in the annotation process, ensuring that the criteria used are consistent and agreed upon by all institutions involved. Although formal annotation guidelines were not strictly necessary, each annotation is validated by at least one additional expert to reduce inconsistencies and ensure fairness in evaluation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Every case has been annotated by medical experts with more than five years of experience in the maxillofacial field.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available in our scenario, meaning that each CBCT volume is annotated by a single expert only, but each produced annotation has been validated or corrected by at least another annotator to reduce possible mistakes.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All the volumes have been rescaled to have the same voxel size (0.3mm isotropic) and rescaled to HU (Hounsfield Unit).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Volumes have been manually annotated by medical experts, but no multiple annotations are available for the same CBCT. We plan to involve different annotators to independently reannotate a portion of each test set ($\geq 20\%$) involved in the challenge. The re-annotation will be performed following the same protocols described in this document and will be used to compare the accuracy of the challenge submissions with the annotators' inter-agreement in the paper describing the challenge results. We do not plan to use such re-annotations for evaluating challenge submissions.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

No other relevant source of error has been identified.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The metrics used to rank the submitted proposals are based on the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), the 95th percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95), and the inference execution time (Time). Clicks will be provided at each interaction step as 3D coordinates alongside CBCT images, with identical, pre-simulated clicks for all participants to ensure fair evaluation. In each interaction step, two clicks (one for each IAC) are accumulated. and this process will proceed incrementally, starting from zero clicks and progressing to the full number of clicks per IAC (5 iterations, 10 clicks in total). To assess how effectively each click improves the segmentation, we will calculate the Area under the Click-to-DSC and Click-to-HD95 curves using the trapezoidal rule. In these curves, the x-axis represents the interaction step, while the y-axis reflects the DSC or HD95 achieved at that step. Additionally, the final DSC and HD95 metrics after all clicks are provided will be used to evaluate the model's overall performance. We will also evaluate the total execution time (Time) over all interaction steps and use it as one of the metrics to

compute the final ranking, as interactive models must be both responsive and efficient to support a real-time human-in-the-loop annotation workflow. Please refer to the ranking method(s) section for more details.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Together with IoU (Intersection over Union), DSC represents the goal standard for the evaluation of segmentation algorithms. Since their meaning is practically the same, there is no reason to preserve both the metrics. The average Hausdorff Distance is a widely used performance measure employed in medical image segmentation as it provides a distance between two points sets, which is extremely relevant in clinical applications.

In order to select the most appropriate metrics, Metrics Reloaded (<https://metrics-reloaded.dkfz.de/>) recommendations have been employed. Among the suggested metrics there was the Dice score, and the Normalized Surface Distance (NSD). Compared to the Hausdorff Distance (HD), the NSD is less sensitive to the outliers. We opted for the HD95 because, as an example, when measuring the distance between the inferior alveolar nerve and the teeth roots, it is mandatory to have the upper bound error and not an average one. This allows practitioners to carefully plan surgical operations for teeth removal while preventing any risk of damaging the nerve

In the context of interactive segmentation, the DSC and HD95 are computed after each interaction step, with accumulating clicks in each step, and are used to compute the: 1) DSC@FinalClick; 2) HD95@FinalClick; 3) the area under the DSC-to-Click curve; 4) and the area under the HD95-to-Click curve.

1-2) The DSC@FinalClick and HD95@FinalClick measure the final segmentation quality of the IACs in the CBCT volumes after all user clicks have been provided. These metrics reflect the model's ability to deliver accurate and clinically meaningful results at the conclusion of the interactive process.

3-4) The areas under the DSC-to-Click (higher=better) and HD95-to-Click (lower=better) curves capture how effectively the model leverages each user click to improve segmentation quality. This metric demonstrates the proficiency of the model in refining IAC segmentations with minimal user interaction, ensuring practicality for clinical workflows.

These metrics allow us to select the best interactive methods and standardize them in a common framework. To ensure long-term impact, the best interactive methods from the challenge could be integrated into the open-source MONAI Label framework as 3D Slicer plugins. This would establish a reproducible, structured workflow, enabling the community to seamlessly adopt cutting-edge CBCT-based IAC annotation tools with minimal effort and a standardized API.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking schema involves the following steps:

1. For each branch of the IAC (left and right) and for each volume, calculate the four metrics: (a) DSC@FinalClick;

(b) HD95@FinalClick; (c) DSC-to-Click AUC; and (d) HD95-to-Click AUC, for a fixed number of 5 interaction steps.

The result will be 4 metrics * 2 IAC branches, 8 scores in total.

Measure also (e) average inference time of the five interaction steps (Time); and (f) maximum used memory (Mem), for all cases;

2. Average the four DSC- and HD95-based metrics for each IAC branch across all volumes.

3. Rank all the ten metrics, independently;

4. Average the eight rankings obtained at point 3 for each DSC- and HD95-based metric and the rankings obtained for Time to produce the final rank (9 ranking in total);

5. If two or more final ranks obtained at point 4 are equal, use Mem ranking to break ties;

6. If two or more ranks are still equal, it is a tie: the prize will be evenly split.

Please refer to <https://github.com/AlmageLab-zip/ToothFairy/blob/main/ToothFairy3/Interactive-Segmentation/evaluation/evaluation.py> for the actual implementation, probably easier to understand than written text.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm does not produce any result for a specific CBCT volume we will consider the predicted segmentation as a volume of 0s, meaning that the Dice score for that image will be equal to 0 for each IAC for all interaction steps, and the HD95 will be equal to the diagonal of the volume.

Furthermore, the average inference time will be set to 10 minutes.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

There is no interdependence between patients/cases. Each CBCT (both in train and test) belongs to a different patient and has been annotated by only one expert. The selected metrics will provide homogeneous numbers on different patients that can be later averaged to provide the final rank on a specific class/metric. Different metrics (i.e., DSC and Hausdorff distance) calculated separately on each class are later aggregated to produce the final ranking.

To ensure robustness in the final ranking, the recommendations provided by Maier et al. [1*] have been followed. In general, there are two contrasting approaches to aggregate metrics across the test cases. The first approach, known as metric-based aggregation, involves initially aggregating metric values across all test cases (e.g., using mean or median), and then ranking the algorithms on the aggregated value. The second approach is the case-based aggregation, which starts by calculating a rank for each test case, and then the final rank is determined by aggregating the ranks of the test cases. According to the paper by Maier et al. [1*] the single-metric rankings (specifically for DSC-based and HD95-based metrics in our case) demonstrate higher statistical robustness when employing metric-based aggregation and using the mean instead of the median for aggregation.

[1*] Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A., Onogur, S., Stankovic, M., Scholz, P., Arbel, T., Bogunovic, H., Bradley, A.P., Carass, A., et al., 2018. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. *Nature Communications* 9, 5217

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will perform bootstrapping to assess ranking uncertainty.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The final top-ranked participant will represent the optimal balance of model effectiveness and model latency. Although the top-ranked method may not be the most effective in terms of DSC and HD95, it will be the easiest method to integrate into daily clinical practice, as it predicts effective results close to the state of the art while providing these results at a reasonable latency, as well as allowing the clinician to quickly refine the model predictions. Furthermore, the actual metric values are converted to per-metric rankings to increase the variability across methods, and the final post-challenge ranking of the submissions will be determined using bootstrapping to limit the selection bias for the volumes in the test set.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the challenge summary paper we plan to discuss and evaluate ranking variability, inter-algorithm variability, and the combination of submitted algorithms via ensembling.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

[1] Bolelli, F., Lumetti, L., Vinayahalingam, S., Di Bartolomeo, M., Pellacani, A., Marchesini, K., ... & Grana, C. (2024). Segmenting the Inferior Alveolar Canal in CBCTs Volumes: the ToothFairy Challenge. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*.

[2] Lumetti, L., Pipoli, V., Bolelli, F., Ficarra, E., & Grana, C. (2024). Enhancing Patch-Based Learning for the Segmentation of the Mandibular Canal. *IEEE Access*.

[3] Achraf Ben-Hamadou, Nour Neifar, Ahmed Rekik, Oussama Smaoui, Firas Bouzguenda, Sergi Pujades, Edmond Boyer, Edouard Ladroit "Teeth3DS+: An Extended Benchmark for Intraoral 3D Scans Analysis" arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.06094, 2022.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

As already mentioned in the introductory description of the challenge and inside task details, we aim for this challenge to be part of a biggest enclosing workshop: ODIN2025. The workshop aims to present and discuss challenge results, including STSR - Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration challenge submitted as a separate satellite event of MICCAI2025, and create a consortium for dental-related AI researchers. Through a combination of keynote talks, technical sessions, and panel discussions, we will foster collaboration, exchange ideas, and identify the unique challenges in the field. Our vision is to establish a robust and sustainable community that convenes regularly, creating a platform to advance the field and drive impactful innovation.